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The article focuses on the feasibility of using artificial intelligence and blockchain to address the challenge of improving textbooks by embedding education for sustainable development in them. The problems of textbook content and pedagogy renewal from the perspective of the Global Action Programme on Education for Sustainable Development and its Roadmap 2030 are considered. UNESCO reports on the status of these challenges and the potential of artificial intelligence combined with blockchain to facilitate this process are analysed. It is concluded that artificial intelligence combined with blockchain can be used to create a new generation of textbooks by integrating education for sustainable development into the subject area of the curriculum, as well as assessing student performance in developing the core competencies of education for sustainable development. Solving this task will provide a platform for the next step - combining subject-specific learning and education for sustainable development into a unified interdisciplinary system of problem-oriented education, implementing a whole-institution approach to ESD in educational ecosystems of different levels.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, blockchain, textbooks, education for sustainable development.

In the world today, people have stopped noticing that they use AI on a day-to-day basis in their ordinary lives (reading emails, translators, voice assistants). AI has learned to plan, solve problems, give advice, and even learn.

The UNESCO report "Steering AI and advanced ICTs for Knowledge Societies/A rights, openness, access and multi-stakeholder perspective" (2019) focuses on the governance of AI and advanced ICTs in digital societies [1]. Ideas from leading AI experts show that AI technologies have enormous potential in different spheres of modern human life. Looking at the range of help from AI, the report proposes assessing the development of artificial intelligence through ROAM indicators in key categories: Human Rights, Openness, Accessibility, Multistakeholder Participation. Recall that these qualities also characterize SDG 4.7: 'Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all' (SDG, 2014) [2]. However, there are also some challenges in assisting AI education. These relate to ensuring equality of opportunity for children from different countries and social groups to use AI: around 40% of the world's population still does not have access to the Internet. This means that many students have limited access to the information they need to learn, as well as limited opportunities to create and share electronic data [3]

Despite the challenges of use, the potential for the development of AI is great. Technological trends in AI development in the coming years relate to AI learning sequential learning, optimal ways of problem solving (faster and more efficient), handwritten digit recognition, etc.

The correct and effective use of AI allows

- shorten the time required to learn new learning material,
- adapt learning (content and pace) to the child, not the other way around;
- to catalyse the absorption of new material by presenting it in different ways;

- to create individual educational trajectories for students, taking into account their abilities (strengths and weaknesses) and the objectives set;

- to take the educational process out of the school walls (in which the student learns not the world around him/her, but the information about it) and into the real environment [4].

It is believed that AI will make it possible to assess a child's learning not only on the basis of his grades and attendance but also on the work of the class itself, including the display of personal qualities such as perseverance, confidence, interest ... That is, assessment will include not only academic success, but also personal results. Unlike AI, traditional forms of assessment are not well suited to assessing general cultural skills, communication skills, moral characteristic, ability to interact, cooperate and work effectively in a team. Meanwhile, they are just as important for life in the 21st century. AI will help curriculum developers expand their information base, incorporate information from different sources and make connections between different data. This will increase the reliability of predictions and adjust course content in real time.

AI can be useful for implementing a whole-institution approach to implementing ESD within an educational organisation, even if its branches are located in different countries, as well as taking into account the educational ecosystem capabilities of the place of residence, city, region. That is, AI is an opportunity to work with big data. According to the International Data Corporation (IDC) the world's data growth is 40% annually, expected to reach 163 trillion gigabytes by 2025.

In this context, we justify the prospect of using AI in alliance with blockchain [наши 5,6]. Blockchain is a new and robust technology for generating and storing records, which uses a distributed database and opens wide horizons for new high-tech projects. The knowledge base in many subject areas, especially in science and technology, is rapidly changing, expanding. A course of study can become obsolete as early as

the approval stage. The alliance between AI and blockchain is the ability to use large amounts of data, analyse it and reflect the findings through visualisation tools, helping curriculum developers to improve the relevance and accuracy of the information available, as well as the competence of the developers themselves. The advantages of blockchain are the high security of its transactions; the transparency of the flow of information; the preservation of the anonymity of private information; and the distributed storage of information. The latter means an ordered database on all the computers of network participants. This means that any changes to the database are recorded for all users. The timing of changes is noted, and a link to the previous block is given. All users of the blockchain can see that a transaction is taking place. It is impossible to change, delete, damage one or more blocks - this requires "permission" from all participants in the vast system. The actual content of the transaction is protected by your private key. The transaction is visible to all users and its contents are confidential and secure. Blockchain is publicly available and useful where there are many participants in the process. It eliminates the need for trusted intermediaries and experts, as well as central controller access to verify transactions and authenticate their source [7].

AI in alliance with blockchain - useful for ecosystems in education: a network of educational organisations that use a distributed database together. Such an alliance eliminates mistrust in the system: one organisation will not allow another to make changes to its records in the database for economic or political interests. Proof of authorisation and proof of credibility increase. This is important to prove authorship, the credibility of teachers' diplomas, the contents of educational subjects' portfolios (since it is not possible to "add" an author to the database or change the date of an entry), and to create a barrier to plagiarism. Consistency of records allows to build a history of events, information on the dynamics of progress, personal learning trajectories. Blockchain, as a digital cluster for records and changes in the network, stores as long as programmed records of a child's developmental dynamics, successes and challenges, etc. , actual any type of information in the world.

Despite the great advances and prospects of AI and blockchain in education, all researchers conclude that there is currently no technology that can replace the teacher, the live communication with the teacher. New technologies have only reinforced and confirmed the teacher's priority role in education. As David Thornburgh put it, "any teacher who can be replaced by a computer deserves it [8].

Steven Duggan's review concludes that "although adoption of AI is still at a very early stage" - it should "be used for good, and therefore earn our trust once the questions arising from its use are answered" [3].

Despite the active exploration of AI and blockchain, there are still many blind spots on the map of its use in education. In particular, these relate to updating textbooks for ESD implementation.

Even in this increasingly digital age, school textbooks remain an important part of the curriculum [9].

Textbooks remain an area of untapped opportunity in integrating sustainable development into formal education through AI and blockchain technologies.

UNESCO (2016) Global education monitoring report 'Textbooks paving the way to sustainable development' highlights that the textbook is a powerful tool for shaping the minds of children and youth, and calls on governments to urgently update the content of their textbooks in line with the objectives of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development [10]. However, textbooks in many countries are limited to SD information, with no focus on education for sustainable development [11]

The United Nations Decade of Education for Sustainable Development (2005-2014) has made a positive start in reorienting and transforming education towards sustainable development.

The importance of textbooks is undeniable. Textbooks reflect the educational canon of society and the ongoing negotiation processes that shape it. At the same time, textbooks do not change as quickly as curricula do. Textbooks answer the key questions of what knowledge to pass on to the next generation and what competencies to develop. They can make a significant contribution to educating students about peace, human rights, global citizenship and human rights, empowering young people to develop independent opinions free of prejudice.

The recommendations of Sustainable Development - a guide to embedding provide specific guidance to textbook authors on how to 'embed' these into subject textbook content [12].

With the help of the International Society for Education (CIES), UKFIET 2017, UCL Institute of Education (2017) and George Washington University (2018), the Network for Integrating SDG Target 4.7 and Social-Emotional Learning in Educational Materials (NISSEM) was given a soft launch as a resource to facilitate action on SDG Target 4.7. NISSEM notes that the inclusion of SDGs and social-emotional competencies in textbooks should ideally start at a young age [13] In early 2017, a group of international scholars and practitioners came together to promote the inclusion of SDG Target 4.7 and related social and emotional skills (SES) in textbooks. The concept of 'embedding' was further developed in chapter 6. PISA 2018 Global Competence Framework, 2019 [14].

A quantitative, semantic and linguistic (linguocultural and psycho-linguistic) examination of textbooks was required to determine the state of ESD in textbooks. Quantitative analysis determined the percentage of textbooks containing the terms 'sustainable development', 'sustainable development goals'. Semantic analysis aimed at identifying perceptions of environmental and moral imperatives; green economy; sustainable development goals; human rights; global issues of humanity; peace and values of all cultures; natural and cultural heritage in their relationship; environmental, social, economic and cultural ties; links between present and past and future; global citizenship. Linguistic analysis seeks to identify the hidden meanings of the relationship between humans and nature - the 'danger-

ous metaphors' that preserve the anthropocentric attitudes of consumer society. Such analysis is impossible without the use of AI and blockchain technologies. Without them, it is also impossible to update textbooks - their content and pedagogy. Adding (bolting on) information about global issues and SDGs is not enough [11].

ESD goes far beyond education 'about' sustainable development. In Chapter 36 of Agenda 21 (1992), there was a call for the integration of education for sustainable development into the curriculum as a combination of development education and environmental education - in all disciplines. There has long been an international consensus that ESD should be 'embedded throughout the curriculum, not as a separate subject'. Underlying these calls for an interdisciplinary and integrated approach to ESD is a keen awareness of the cross-cutting and interconnected nature of sustainable development.

Progress in addressing this challenge goes from denying the need to change the content and pedagogy of textbooks, to mechanically adding information about SD, then to embedding ESD ideas in curriculum content and other aspects of formal education as an integral element of it, rather than as a 'bolt-on' (bolt-on). ESD is placed at the core of every subject rather than remaining on the periphery of the curriculum. The next step is to merge ESD and the subject matter, including restructuring existing institutional structures [15].

Embedding ESD in textbooks will in the long run lead to a 'holistic system' and as a consequence a redesign of all education, an 'educational paradigm shift' [16]

The implementation of ESD should take place within an institution-wide approach ('the whole school'), the values and principles of SD should be reflected in the mission of the school and be central to the professional development of its teachers. That is, changes need to occur not only in textbooks but also in educational policies, curricula, teacher training and student assessment.

ESD will become so deeply embedded in all forms of education that it becomes indistinguishable as a fundamental value of life, as a social norm. While the embedded element is still discernible (each subject has two educational objectives), its fusion with the system (integration, infusion) offers the possibility of its transformation from within, paving the way for interdisciplinarity and problem-based learning. ESD and the educational process become indistinguishable [17].

To ensure that ESD does not remain on the margins of academic subjects and does not compete for space in an overcrowded curriculum, a systematic, interdisciplinary re-engineering of all content and teaching methods is required, above all the 'mothballed' textbooks. Nor is it about abolishing or minimising the importance of academic content. On the contrary, it is about reorienting subjects to more socially and globally relevant goals and raising the rank of subject content – from the private to the general, understanding its role in life, the future, and improving the quality of education.

Accordingly, the assessment of educational outcomes is also changing - not only promoting the cognitive development of the student, but also developing the

skills, knowledge, values and attitudes necessary for responsible, active and productive citizenship, developing key competences that enable one to navigate in an increasingly complex world and interact with it creatively and responsibly. There is a need to learn how to measure these competencies. Without the technological union of AI and blockchain, limiting this to traditional methods, it is practically impossible to do this for all subjects in continuity across educational levels, taking into account local factors and country specifics.

Conclusions. Solving the global problems facing humanity in the 21st century is impossible without renewing the content and pedagogy of education around the world. This ambitious task is being tackled in stages, through the incorporation and then introduction of ESD into the content of textbooks, curricula, assessment systems, and all areas of the work of all educational organizations. Such an ambitious global task can only be achieved by harnessing the increasing power of artificial intelligence technology in alliance with blockchain, and requires a strong effort, given that the window of opportunity in a rapidly changing, unstable world may soon close.

References

1. UNESCO report "Steering AI and advanced ICTs for Knowledge Societies/A rights, openness, access and multi-stakeholder perspective" (2019) focuses on the governance of AI and advanced ICTs in digital societies [1].
2. SDG (2014). The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. UNESCO. Paris, France. Retrieved from <https://www.eda.admin.ch/agenda2030/en/home/agenda-2030/die17-ziele-fuer-eine-nachhaltige-entwicklung.htm>
3. Искусственный интеллект в образовании: Изменение темпов обучения. Аналитическая записка ИИТО ЮНЕСКО / Стивен Даггэн; ред. С.Ю. Князева; пер. с англ.: А.В. Паршакова. — Москва : Институт ЮНЕСКО по информационным технологиям в образовании, 2020.
4. Non-state actors in education Who chooses? Who loses? Attribution-ShareAlike 3.0 IGO (CC-BY-SA 3.0 IGO) licence <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/igo/>.
5. Dziatkovskii A. Artificial intelligence and blockchain interaction in the context of inclusive education// Proceedings of the XXXVI International Multidisciplinary Conference «Recent Scientific Investigation». Primedia E-launch LLC. Shawnee, USA. 2022. DOI:10.32743/UsaConf.2022.9.36.344687
6. Dziatkovskii A. (2022) IoT Technology Based on AI Platform for Blockchain E-education. World Science. 6(78). doi: 10.31435/rsglobal_ws/30122022/7906
7. Dziatkovskii A. Education through the lens of blockchain and vice versa // Journal of Modern Education Review (ISSN 2155-7993, USA), Academic Star Publishing Company, 2021, Issue 6.
8. UNESCO (2021). Global Education Monitoring Report 2021/2: Non-state actors in education: Who chooses? Who loses? Paris, UNESCO.

9. Georgescu, D. & Bernard, J. (2007). Thinking and building peace through innovative textbook design. In C. Peterson (ed). Report of the inter-regional experts' meeting on developing guidelines for promoting peace and intercultural understanding through curricula, textbooks and learning materials. Section for Inclusion and Quality Learning Enhancement Division for the Promotion of Basic Education, Sector UNESCO7, Paris FRANCE. UNESCO International Bureau of Education PO Box 1991211 Geneva 20 SWITZERLAND Paris. 46 p.
10. UNESCO (2016) Global education monitoring report 'Textbooks paving the way to sustainable development' <https://gcedclearinghouse.org/sites/default/files/resources/246777e.pdf>
11. Sinicrope, C., J. Norris and Y. Watanabe (2007) Understanding and Assessing Intercultural Competence: A Summary of Theory, Research and Practice, Technical Report for the Foreign Language Program Evaluation Project. Second Language Studies, 26/1, 1-58. <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download;jsessionid=D8D4BDBE0C5918D895EFC04B36C738E4?doi=10.1.1.517.1193&rep=rep1&type=pdf>.
12. Textbooks for Sustainable Development: A Guide to Embedding (2017). Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Education for Peace and Sustainable Development, New Delhi, India © UNESCO MGIEP, 188.
13. Sinclair, M. (2018). Social and Emotional, Cognitive and Behavioral Learning for Well-Being, Global (Including National and Local) Citizenship and Sustainable Development at Different Levels of Education: Focus on Adolescence NISSEM Working Paper. NISSEM Working Paper. https://www.nissem.org/sites/default/files/nissem_working_paper.pdf
14. OECD (2019), CHAPTER 6. "PISA 2018 Global Competence Framework", in PISA 2018 Assessment and Analytical Framework, OECD Publishing, Paris, 165-215. <https://doi.org/10.1787/b25efab8-en>.
15. Dzyatkovskaya E.N. et al Textbooks for SD: social responsibility of authors (2020). The Annual International Conference on Cognitive - Social, and Behavioural Sciences 9th icCSBs. <https://www.europeanproceedings.com/article/10.15405/epes.20121.5>
16. Lotz-Sisitka, H., Wals, A., Kronlid, D., & McGarry, D. (2015). Transformative, transgressive social learning: rethinking higher education pedagogy in times of systemic global dysfunction. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 16, 73-80
17. Textbooks for Sustainable Development: A Guide to Embedding (2017). Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Education for Peace and Sustainable Development, New Delhi, India © UNESCO MGIEP, 188.